

FINITE ELEMENT MODELLING OF 3D WOVEN COMPOSITES FOR STIFFNESS PREDICTION

PG Biragoni and SR Hallett

Advanced Composites Centre for Innovation and Science, University of Bristol, Queens Building, university Walk, BS8 1TR, UK
praveen.biragoni@bristol.ac.uk

SUMMARY

A domain superposition technique has been proposed for modelling woven fabric composites. This has been applied to 3D woven composite unit cell models for a number of different internal architectures to obtain the full stiffness matrices. A particular advantage is the reduction in model size required compared to conventional finite element methods.

Keywords: 3D woven composites, finite element modelling, unit cell

1 INTRODUCTION

Composite materials with woven fabric reinforcement have become increasingly popular for use in structural applications in recent years due to their advantages such as low fabrication costs, light weight, ease of handling and high adaptability, over tape laminates and several other engineering materials.

As interest in the use of composite materials for structural applications continues to increase, alternative reinforcements to conventional pre-preg systems are being more widely considered. 3-D woven composites are gaining increased prominence due to their ability to produce near net shape preforms as well as integrated third direction reinforcement. The important characteristics of 3-D woven preforms that make them suitable for composites are high axial rigidity, flexibility, formability and stability. One of the barriers to their advancement and increased use is the difficulties associated with creating numerical models to predict their performance. This is predominantly due to the complexity of the internal architectures which result in large finite element models and produce highly degenerated inter-tow regions which are difficult to mesh. Due to the almost infinite possibilities for variation in architecture created by the weaving process, it is highly desirable to have a predictive capability to reduce physical testing and aid design. In this paper a method for predicting the stiffness of two characteristic 3D woven architecture styles is presented and compared to experimental data where available.

Literature reviews [1, 2] show that finite element (FE) analysis and analytical methods are powerful tools for studying the mechanical properties of woven reinforcements. However, the complexity of the micro-structure is proportional to the number of parameters controlling the mechanical properties. So, various finite element techniques and assumptions have been proposed for simplifying the analysis. Most of the models for woven reinforced composites are based on the definition of a unit-cell geometry and include the major architectural parameters in predicting the mechanical properties. One of the fundamental difficulties faced in modelling the detailed unit cell

is to build a geometry free from interpenetration at tow crossovers. Another significant problem is that a very fine FE mesh is required to deal with the degenerated volumes of the resin pockets between tows. This can lead to very large FE models exceeding a million degrees of freedom to model a single unit cell, which is only a very small part of the structure. An FE method, known as the ‘binary model’, was developed by Cox et al. [3-6], for simulating woven textile composites. In this model, the axial properties of tows were represented by two-noded line elements possessing axial rigidity, while the transverse stiffness, shear stiffness, and Poisson’s effect of the composite were represented by eight-node solid ‘effective medium’ elements. Due to the simplified assumptions, a complex parameter calibration is needed to yield good correlation which could still be mesh size dependent. Another significant simplification is that the detailed tow geometric features are omitted, making the actual stress calculation process quite complex.

Figure 1 An example for DST mesh for Layer-to-Layer composite

A Domain Superposition Technique (DST) has been previously proposed [7] which is able to overcome a number of traditional difficulties in creating finite element models of composites with complex internal architecture. Here this technique is further developed to evaluate the full set of stiffness properties for a number of complex 3D woven fabric reinforcements.

2 MODELLING TECHNIQUE

A Domain Superposition Technique (DST) has been proposed for the simulation of woven fabric composites [7]. Instead of explicitly modelling the tows and the likely degenerated resin pocket regions among tows, DST separately models the tow region and the matrix region which are both non-degenerated, and can thus be easily discretized using the traditional solid elements. A modified material model is used for tow elements. Material properties of elements in the same space are subtracted from each other. If the initial tow elements have properties assigned as tow minus matrix, then when the matrix properties are added, only the tow properties remain. The two regions are then superimposed by coupling them together. In contrast to other mesh superposition methods which require iterative procedures [8-10], DST is conceptually concise and much simpler to implement.

Compared with traditional FE models, DST has significant advantages. Using standard FE methods for modelling woven textile composites with solid elements requires a very fine mesh to deal with the highly degenerated volumes of the resin between tows. It is also difficult to build a geometry free from interpenetration at tow crossovers. DST by comparison explicitly meshes the tow domain and the global domain separately and the final result is simply the superposition of the two domains using coupling equations.

3 APPLICATION TO 3D WOVEN FABRICS

Following initial successful development on 2D weave structures DST has been further applied to more complex 3D woven architectures. Two different weave architectures of Orthogonal and Layer-to-Layer fabrics have been successfully simulated using DST and the full stiffness matrices obtained. Initially idealised tow geometry has been used, which slightly under estimates fibre volume fraction (vf). When results are normalised by vf, credible results are obtained which can be compared to experimental results when available. A mesh sensitivity study has been conducted showing that good results are still obtained even when a relatively coarse mesh is used. This can be an order of magnitude fewer elements compared to conventional FE models. Figure 1 shows an example of a typical DST model.

The textile geometric modelling software, TexGen [11] was used to generate these complex weave types (Figure 2), as it is time consuming and difficult to model them with conventional CAD and finite element pre-processing software. The models were also meshed in TexGen with 8-noded brick elements and 6-noded wedge elements by using user written python code, making sure of the correct element orientation, to generate an output file. These mesh files were then converted into ANSYS readable input files and exported to ANSYS where the analysis was done.

Figure 2 a) Layer-to-Layer and b) Orthogonal weave model

4 RESULTS

4.1 Mesh dependency studies

Some of the models from the literature, such as the “binary model” [3-6], can be mesh size dependant due to the discrete nature of the reinforcement modelling, even though they have the advantage of substantially smaller model. That is to say, when the FE mesh is refined further, the results will change continuously rather than converge to the real state as the modelled structure should behave. In contrast, DST is mesh density objective, i.e. the simulation results will converge if the meshes are fine enough. This is due to the fact that the tow cross-section geometry is explicitly modelled through the use of solid elements. There is therefore no change in the relative position of the tows within the matrix mesh with mesh refinement.

Mesh dependency studies were performed to understand and observe the performance of DST and the results for one of the models is presented in this paper, see table 1. The study was done on three different meshes of the Layer-to-Layer weave style, see Figure 3. One of them is the mesh directly obtained from TexGen without changing the default seed size and other parameters like number of slave nodes and section points, which is called the standard mesh in this paper. The second mesh is the coarse mesh, generated by increasing the seed size and decreasing the number of slave nodes and section points. The third mesh is the fine mesh, generated by decreasing the seed size and increasing the number of slave nodes and section points. The three different meshes were numerically analyzed for the full set of stiffness properties and are compared in table 1. It is observed from the results that even with less than 15 % of the elements and nodes of those used in the standard mesh (note: mesh used in the conventional FEM should be finer than this, so as to deal with the resin rich regions), the results are not much different to those obtained by using standard mesh. For the

stiffness in the warp and weft directions the error is between 1- 3%, for through thickness it is 6.9 % and for shear stiffness it is less than 1.5% in all the planes except for the x-y plane (warp direction), which is 4.8%. This can be considered as outstanding and can make a significant difference especially when modelling at the structural sub-component level.

Table 1 Mesh sensitivity study on Layer-to-Layer weave model.

Stiffness properties (GPa)	Fine mesh	Standard mesh	Coarse mesh	(Standard/fine)*100	(Coarse/Standard)*100
E-warp	72.99	72.82	71.40	99.76%	98.1%
E-weft	68.22	68.20	66.28	99.97%	97.2%
E-thickness	12.63	12.62	12.1	99.92%	95.88%
Gxy-warp	6.17	6.25	5.95	101.26%	95.2%
Gxy-weft	6.64	6.49	6.54	97.79%	100.7%
Gyz-weft	4.86	4.80	4.75	98.87%	99%
Gyz-thick	5.15	4.93	4.94	95.71%	100.2%
Gxz-warp	4.51	4.47	4.42	99.11%	99%
Gxz-thick	4.91	4.73	4.66	96.33%	98.6%
No of Elements*	62,148	26,788	3,940	43.1%	14.7%
No of Nodes*	94,935	41,645	6,275	43.9%	15%

* No of elements and No of nodes include those of matrix also.

Figure 3 DST meshes: Mesh dependency study on Layer-to-Layer composite

4.2 Comparison between DST and Conventional FE analysis

To fully understand and validate the domain superposition technique, DST was performed on two weave styles, Orthogonal and Layer-to-Layer fabrics. A commercial finite element analysis program (ANSYS) was used. The geometry of the representative volume element (RVE) analyzed is given in Figure 2. Periodic boundary conditions are implemented in-plane and an applied differential displacement between nodal pairs on opposite faces is given in the loading direction [12]. In the figure, X is the warp direction and Z is the weft direction. Brick elements are used throughout for the structural discretisation in the DST models. The material elastic constants used for the numerical analysis are $E = 3.4\text{GPa}$ and $\nu = 0.315$ for the matrix material, and $E_1 = 221\text{GPa}$, $E_2 = 17.2\text{GPa}$, $E_3 = 17.2\text{GPa}$, $\nu_{12} = \nu_{13} = 0.293$, $\nu_{23} = 0.412$ and $G_{12} = G_{13} = 10.08$, $G_{23} = 4.919\text{GPa}$ for the tow material.

DST has been successfully validated for the tensile loading mode for the Orthogonal and Layer-to-Layer models by comparing results with conventional FE analysis (courtesy of University of Nottingham). The DST results are generally in good agreement with Conventional FE results. It should be noted that DST results were obtained with as little as 3% of the number of elements of those from traditional FE analysis. The worst correlation was in the through-thickness direction which as was noted in table 2 was the most sensitive to mesh density. As far as comparison with experimental results is concerned it should be noted that the geometry used has been highly idealized. This has resulted in a lower than realistic volume fraction since the warp and weft tows are completely straight and the amount of nesting is therefore greatly reduced. The stiffness can be normalized by fibre volume fraction to compare

with experimental results but this will still not take account of any tow crimp which will reduce the stiffness compared to perfectly straight tows. The DST model also assumes perfect bonding between matrix and fiber material by coupling them together. No defects were modeled in the DST model. In the composite specimens, defects and imperfect bonding can exist which will reduce the modulus value.

Figure 4 Tensile loading applied to Layer-to-Layer composite model

Table 2 Comparison between DST and Conventional FEM results for stiffness properties (GPa)

Fabric type	Warp direction		Weft direction		Through-thickness	
	DST	FEM	DST	FEM	DST	FEM
Layer-to-Layer	72.82	72.9	68.2	68.97	12.62	9.01
Orthogonal	71.12	67.9	73.52	72.7	12.01	9.34

CONCLUSION

In this work the Domain Superposition Technique has been further developed to evaluate stiffness in all directions for complex 3D woven composites like Orthogonal and Layer-to-Layer weave styles. An excellent correlation is obtained between DST and Conventional FE analysis for the available results so far. As far as comparison of DST with available experimental results is concerned, it is difficult to make clear comparisons due to the assumed perfect geometry. This is not a deficiency of the DST method itself but indicates the need for being able to include more realistic geometry in models now that an efficient analysis technique has been developed which can make use of such information. This is the subject of future work and one in which techniques are already being developed by both the current authors [13] and other researchers [14] for both experimental characterization and numerical prediction.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work has been supported by the 3D SIMCOMS consortium and the Technology Strategy Board. The Technology Strategy Board is a business-led executive non-departmental public body, established by the government. Its mission is to promote and support research into, and development and exploitation of, technology and innovation for the benefit of UK business, in order to increase economic growth and improve the quality of life. It is sponsored by the Department for Innovation, Universities and Skills (DIUS). Please visit www.innovateuk.org for further information.

Thanks also to Dr Jon Crookston and Prof. Nick Warrior of the University of Nottingham for the conventional finite element model results.

REFERENCES

1. Tan P, Tong L, Steven GP (1997) Modelling for predicting the mechanical properties of textile composites - A review. *Composite Part A –Applied Science and Manufacturing* 28(11): 903-922.
2. Crookston JJ, Long AC, Jones IA (2005) A summary review of mechanical properties prediction methods for textile reinforced polymer composites. *Proc. IMechE, Part L: J. Materials: Design and Applications* 219: 91-109.
3. Cox BN, Carter WC, Fleck NA (1994) A binary model of textile composites- I Formulation. *ACTA Metallurgica Et Materialia* 42 (10):3463-3479.
4. Xu J, Cox BN, McGlockton MA, Carter WC (1995) A binary model of textile composites-II. The elastic regime. *Acta Metall. Mater* 43 (9):3511-3524.
5. McGlockton MA, Cox BN, McMeeking RM (2003) A binary model of textile composites: III high failure strain and work of fracture in 3D weaves. *Journal of the Mechanics and Physics of Solids* 51: 1573-1600.
6. Yang QD, Cox B (2003) Spatially averaged local strains in textile composites via the binary model formulation Source. *Journal of Engineering Materials and Technology – Transactions of the ASME*, 125 (4): 418-425.

7. Jiang W.G., Hallett S.R., Wisnom M.R., Development of Domain Superposition Technique for the Modelling of Woven Fabric Composites, in Mechanical Response of Composites,” edited by P. P. Camanho, C. G. Dávila, S. T. Pinho and J. J. C. Remmers, Springer, 2008.
8. Fisher J, Markolefas S, Guttal R, Nayak P (1994) On adaptive multilevel superposition of finite element meshes for linear elastostatics. Applied Numerical Mathematics, 14(1-3): 135-64.
9. Fish J, Yu Q, Shek K (1999) Computational damage mechanics for composite materials based on mathematical homogenization. International Journal for Numerical Methods in Engineering. 45(11): 1657-1679.
10. Zako M, Kurashiki T, Nakai H, Imura M (2007) A multiscale analysis for textile composite materials to evaluate the mechanical properties. Sixteenth International Conference on Composite Materials, July 8-13, Kyoto, Japan.
11. http://texgen.sourceforge.net/index.php/Main_Page.
12. Jiang WG, Henshall JL (2006) Analysis of composite laminate beams using coupling cross section finite element method. Appl Math Mech 27:1709–1718
13. Mahadik Y and Hallett SR, Finite Element Modeling of Tow Geometry in 3D Woven Fabrics, 9th International Conference on Textile Composites (TEXCOMP9), Delaware, 2008
14. Iarve E, Whitney T; Mollenhauer D, Zhou E, Modeling of Complex Fiber Architecture Composites Using the Independent Mesh Method, 48th AIAA/ASME/ASCE/AHS/ASC Structures, Structural Dynamics, and Materials Conference, Honolulu, Hawaii, 2007